

Research

Exploring Anxiety Levels in English Speaking Skills Acquisition among 6th Class Students as Second Language Learners: A Case Study of Shah Latif High School, Pakistan

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Abstract: The primary objective of this study is to investigate the underlying causes of anxiety experienced by sixth-grade students while acquiring English as a second language at the elementary level. A combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods was employed, utilizing the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) instrument developed by Horwitz (1986), along with a case study approach. The study encompassed a population of 30 female and 20 male students, as well as two teachers from Shah Latif School. The findings of the study revealed a significant level of anxiety among students when it came to speaking English. Out of the total 42 students, all exhibited a high level of anxiety. The factors contributing to this anxiety can be categorized into three main aspects: fear of failure, test anxiety, communication apprehension, and fear of negative evaluation. These factors have a profound impact on students' confidence, performance, and participation. To promote a balanced learning environment, it is imperative for the administration, staff, and teachers to collaborate and implement a variety of techniques, strategies, and skills that alleviate anxiety among students. By doing so, the goal is to create a supportive atmosphere that enables all students to feel at ease.

Keywords: Anxiety, Second Language Acquisition, Influencing Factors, Fear of Failure, Communication Apprehension, Negative Evaluation

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Introduction

English holds a prominent position as a global language, serving as a means of communication across countries, transcending barriers in business, industry, cultural heritage, and politics. The widespread globalization of the English language has led to increased demand for English proficiency in various domains.

Language anxiety is a well-documented phenomenon that has garnered significant attention in language acquisition research for several decades. In the context of second or foreign language teaching, language anxiety has long been recognized as an obstacle. Language anxiety, in general, is a negative psychological state that can adversely impact the perception and acquisition of the target language. It has been identified as a significant factor in foreign language learning (Baş & Özcan, 2018; Dörnyei, 2014; Eddie & Aziz, 2020; Goh & Aziz, 2020; Gardner & MacIntyre, 1992).

Over the past few years, language anxiety has been the subject of extensive research. Previous studies on language anxiety have revealed that anxiety can impede foreign language learning outcomes and progress. Language learners often encounter various challenges in learning a foreign language, which can contribute to stress and anxiety, especially at the school level (Capan & Simsek, 2012).

Alrabai (2014) highlighted that language anxiety is a multifaceted construct that encompasses students' behavior, cognition, social interactions, and emotions. He further emphasized that the feeling of tension and apprehension specifically related to second language aspects, such as reading, speaking, writing, listening, and learning, differs from a general sense of anxiety and hinders students from achieving their goals. Studies by Basith et al. (2019) and Miskam and Saidalvi (2019) suggest that undergraduate students often experience speaking anxiety, which hampers their learning and impedes their ability to communicate fluently in English.

English is widely used as a first language or mother tongue in the two major advanced countries, the United States and Great Britain. Approximately half of the global population uses English on a daily basis. Language anxiety is a crucial factor that influences one's level of success in foreign language learning. In the case of English, even a moderate level of anxiety can hinder students' learning progress, significantly impacting their willingness to express their viewpoints and speak fluently (Cagatay, 2015; Wu & Lin, 2014).

Anxiety is prevalent not only in English as a Second Language (ESL) and English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes but also across various categories of language classes. In the Pakistani context, feelings of negativity, sadness, and fear are frequently observed in ESL and EFL classes, affecting students' comprehension and participation (Khattak et al., 2011). This issue has been addressed and studied since the 1960s, from Scovel's time to Chastain and Kleinmann's era to Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope's period (Cagatay, 2015; Dordinejad & Ahmadabad, 2014; Horwitz, 2001).

Research Questions:

1. What are underlying factors contributing to anxiety among Level 6 English as Second Language students?
2. Which factors influence students and contribute to feelings of anxiety, hesitation, and shyness?
3. Are there any viable measures available to address these issues and provide effective remedies?

Purpose of the Study

The research conducted aims to explore the underlying causes of anxiety among 6th-grade students who are learning English as a second language at Shah Latif High School in Pakistan. The study seeks to shed light on the realities faced by these students, particularly their lack of confidence, shyness, pressure, depression, and hesitation when communicating in English. Notably, the research also endeavors to identify effective remedial measures to enhance self-confidence, improve speaking skills, and facilitate fluent discussions in English.

Literature Review

For the purpose of analysis, description, and addressing research gaps, a comprehensive review of previous research papers was conducted. This involved examining various theoretical research papers and relevant articles from different sources. Moreover, more than sixteen research papers focusing on anxiety in second language acquisition (SLA) and English speaking were meticulously reviewed. The aim was to gather diverse perspectives and novel insights, as this particular application of anxiety theory to explore factors related to stress, hesitation, and anxiety in the process of acquiring English as a second language is a novel endeavor, particularly in Sindh, Pakistan. All reviewed papers were sourced from reputable journals, totaling fifteen to sixteen papers, with supplementary information obtained from various credible websites.

Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety

Anxiety, in the context of this study, refers to unpleasant emotions that can manifest as negative assumptions, nervousness, lack of confidence, and apprehension. It is recognized as a characteristic trait or state within the field of educational research. Its prevalence in English classrooms is well-documented, often referred to as pressure, distress, and cognitive hesitation resulting from fear or uneasiness in specific situations. Scholars and researchers have provided various definitions of anxiety, and notable definitions from renowned scholars are as follows:

Elaldi (2016) highlights speaking anxiety as the difficulty to communicate within a group or in front of an audience, which arises in situations such as speech preparation, oral presentations, answering questions, or simple interactions. Udomkit (as cited in Yaikhong & Usaha, 2012) suggests that communication anxiety in the English classroom stems from limited opportunities for students to engage in classroom communication, lack of confidence when speaking English, and other affective factors such as interpersonal evaluation, classroom activities and methods, as well as self-esteem.

In summary, foreign language classrooms present six main sources of anxiety: personal and interpersonal anxiety, learners' beliefs about language anxiety, instructors' beliefs about language learning, instructor-learner interaction, classroom procedures, and testing (Young as cited in Tsiplakides & Keramida, 2009).

Traits of Speaking Anxiety

Leary (as cited in Wilson, 2006) categorizes anxiety traits into three types of behaviors: arousal-mediated responses, disaffiliation behavior, and image protection behavior. Arousal-mediated responses can be observed when students display discomfort, fidget with objects, and exhibit nervousness and stuttering during speech. Disaffiliation behavior manifests as actions aimed at reducing social interaction, such as limiting participation in conversation. Image protection behavior is characterized by frequent smiling, nodding, and minimal interruption of other learners.

On a more extreme end, Mandler and Sarason (as cited in Wilson, 2006) categorize anxious behavior among learners based on five points: perspiration, excessive movement, inappropriate laughter and exclamations, questioning of instructions, and hand movements. Additionally, VonWorde (as cited in Wilson, 2006) notes that anxious students in foreign language classrooms may exhibit physical reactions that may go unnoticed, such as headaches, clammy hands, shaking, sweating, a pounding heart, foot tapping, and desk drumming.

Regarding anxiety traits, another writer, Azarfam & Baki (2012), describes how anxiety is observed in language learners through symptoms such as freezing in class, experiencing mental blanks before exams, feeling hesitant about entering the classroom, difficulty concentrating, forgetfulness, sweating, palpitations, and exhibiting avoidance behaviors such as missing class and delaying homework assignments.

Causes of Foreign Language Anxiety

Regarding the causes of foreign language anxiety, a notable researcher, Boonkit (2010), emphasizes the significance of learners' self-confidence in speaking performance. Building learners' confidence is crucial for minimizing anxiety, as reported by Boonkit, who states that "building up confidence in speaking to an audience was mainly reported as a factor that strengthened speaking performance" (p. 1308).

In connection to Boonkit's ideas, a study conducted by Azarfam and Baki (2012) on Iranian college students revealed that negative assumptions contribute to reduced active participation in various types of classes. The study involved three Iranian learners, and it identified several negative assumptions associated with speaking anxiety. These assumptions included fear of being unable to communicate effectively with teachers or fellow students, fear of making mistakes while speaking English, fear of asking different types of questions in English, and fear of engaging in unimportant discussions. These factors ultimately encouraged the three learners to adopt passive learning approaches.

Young (1991), an esteemed scholar, offers a comprehensive and widely accepted list of potential sources of language anxiety. These sources can be categorized into three main areas: learner-related factors, teacher-related factors, and instructional practices. Young argues that language anxiety arises from:

- Personal and interpersonal anxieties
- Learners' beliefs about language learning
- Instructors' beliefs about language teaching
- Instructor-learner interactions
- Classroom procedures
- Language testing

In his detailed description, Young (1991:428) further highlights that anxiety can be divided into three major phases, which significantly hinder foreign language learners' pursuit of success:

1. If an individual believes that success is guaranteed but later discovers that it is not, debilitating anxiety arises, leading to a lack of effort to succeed.
2. If the person recognizes that success is not guaranteed but acknowledges that making a genuine effort can lead to success, anxiety can motivate them to perform better.
3. If the learner desires success but feels that no matter how hard they try, failure is inevitable, their anxiety exacerbates the situation, making success more elusive (p. 428).

Theoretical Background

According to Horwitz et al. (1986), anxiety can be defined as "a distinct feeling of pressure, uneasiness, fear, and apprehension associated with activation of the autonomic nervous or tactile system." It is widely observed that anxiety has a negative impact on second language (L2) learning and is one of the most extensively studied factors influencing students' experiences during the learning process. The researchers (Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope, 1986) emphasize that foreign language anxiety (FLA) arises from the learners' understanding, emotions, feelings, and behaviors related to language acquisition, which are influenced by the language teaching methodology.

Speaking anxiety specifically pertains to anxiety-related feelings and stress associated with the autonomic nervous system (Horwitz et al., 1986). Students who are excessively anxious about their speaking abilities may become extremely nervous when they make mistakes. Horwitz et al. (1986, p. 127) indicate that anxiety has both positive and negative aspects. Some individuals are more likely to experience a moderate level of anxiety since they do not want to damage their self-confidence and aim to achieve high scores. However, contrary to the norm, most students report that anxiety has a detrimental effect on both their language learning process and their performance.

Furthermore, Horwitz et al. (1986, p. 125) describe three categories of anxiety provided by psychologists: trait anxiety, state anxiety, and situation-specific anxiety. State anxiety is viewed as a response to a specific anxiety-provoking stimulus, such as classrooms or important tests, while trait anxiety is considered a stable characteristic of an individual's personality (Spielberger, 1984:1; MacIntyre and Gardner, 1991:90; Horwitz, 2001:113). The research conducted by Horwitz et al. (1986) suggests that language anxiety is reactivated by specific contexts and is triggered by particular situations, such as public speaking in front of an audience. Anxiety itself is a multifaceted and context-dependent condition.

Language anxiety refers to the feelings of fear and alarm experienced in relation to acquiring a second language, encompassing all four language skills. However, these factors hinder students' actual performance (Horwitz & Young, 1991; Hashemi and Abbasi, 2013; MacIntyre and Gardner, 1994). Recent research in linguistics has confirmed that language learning anxiety is a unique type of anxiety distinct from other types of fears. While some level of anxiety in language learning can be beneficial, the overall impact of negative affect on second language acquisition is usually significant. Although Horwitz et al.'s theory originated primarily from clinical observations and anecdotal evidence, numerous studies have since supported their theoretical model, providing evidence to support their defined concept of anxiety in language learning (Horwitz et al., 1986).

State, Trait, and Situational Anxiety

To further elaborate on the three main terms mentioned above, Pekrun (1992) suggests that "In instances of high anxiety, habitualized reactions can cause individuals who have experienced many threatening situations in the past to be more likely to perceive future situations as threatening." Similarly, Vasey and Daleiden (1996) argue that "highly anxious individuals may have a lower threshold of threat recognition, perceiving generally ambiguous situations as potentially threatening more often than moderately anxious individuals." Given the possibility that certain individuals are more prone to anxiety than others, it is important to differentiate between individuals who frequently experience anxiety and those who do not. Spielberger (1983) briefly describes this differentiation as the state/trait distinction.

Research Methodology

The research method employed in this study utilized a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches to gain a comprehensive understanding of the issue of anxiety among students. The study population consisted of 50 students, comprising thirty female students and twenty male students, from a public school. Additionally, two senior teachers from the same school were also involved in the study.

Over the past decades, it has been a topic of discussion that students in Sindh, particularly when acquiring English as a second language, experience significant pressure and anxiety. The commonality of this issue prompted the investigation. The students included in the study were between the ages of 10 and 15 years.

Data collection involved the use of both qualitative and quantitative methods. Qualitative data was gathered through interviews conducted with the participating teachers. These interviews aimed to explore the sources of pressure, stress, and anxiety experienced by students, specifically focusing on why a considerable number of students in Pakistan face hesitation, what the underlying problems are, and how to effectively manage these challenges.

By employing a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches, the study aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of anxiety among students in the context of acquiring English as a second language.

Data Collection and Instrument:

The research utilized the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) instrument, originally developed by Horwitz in 1986, to assess foreign language classroom anxiety. The FLCAS questionnaire consisted of a total of 33 statements, categorized into different dimensions. Specifically, there were 8 items related to communication anxiety, 9 items related to fear of negative evaluation, 5 items related to test anxiety, and 11 items grouped under the category of anxiety in English classes.

The respondents, including the students and two teachers, were asked to rate each item on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strong disagreement) to 5 (strong agreement). The questionnaire was modified slightly to ensure the collection of authentic and relevant data.

The research was conducted at Shah Shah Latif High School, with a total population of fifty-two participants. All participants were sixth-grade students aged between ten and fifteen years. The data collection process involved the administration of the modified questionnaire to all seated students in the class. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted with the participants, including both students and teachers, to explore potential remedial measures for anxiety management.

Both qualitative and quantitative methods were employed in the data collection process. The collected data was then analyzed to derive meaningful results for the research study.

Data Analysis

The study included all the students from the 6th grade who were studying English as a second language at Shah Latif High School during the academic sessions of 2021-2022. The total number of participants was fifty-two, consisting of fifty students and two teachers. Among the fifty students, thirty were female and twenty were male.

The questionnaire was administered physically at the school premises, and it was distributed to all the present students in their respective classrooms. All the students actively participated in the test, providing their responses to the questionnaire.

The results of the questionnaire were collected and recorded, and the data obtained from the participants were analyzed. The specific tables presenting the results can be provided separately, as they require a visual representation of the data.

Results and Discussion

Findings:

The data for this research was collected from students at Govt. Shah Latif High School in Shikarpur. The research design used for this study was a case study approach, which aimed to classify students based on their level of speaking anxiety and to identify the factors contributing to this anxiety and its impact on their English language acquisition.

The case study consisted of three main steps. Firstly, the researcher identified the specific problems faced by students in the English as a Foreign Language (EFL) class. To gather data, the participants were given the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) questionnaire to assess their levels of speaking anxiety.

Secondly, individual interviews were conducted with each participant, including two teachers, to gain further insights into the factors influencing speaking anxiety. The interviews aimed to delve deeper into the students' experiences and perspectives regarding their anxiety in language learning.

Lastly, the researcher observed the students' performance in the classroom setting to gather additional data. This observation provided an opportunity to assess how speaking anxiety affected their actual performance during English language acquisition activities.

By utilizing a case study design and employing multiple data collection methods, the researcher aimed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the speaking anxiety experienced by students in the EFL class and its implications for their language learning outcomes.

Level of Student’s Speaking Anxiety

Based on the data collected through the modified FLCAS questionnaire, participants were classified into two categories based on their level of anxiety: high level and low level. The questionnaire aimed to identify the factors contributing to the participants' anxiety. The questionnaire consisted of Likert scale options ranging from 1 to 5, with 5 indicating "strongly agree" and 1 indicating "strongly disagree."

After completing the questionnaire, the responses were manually calculated to determine the participants' anxiety levels. Positive answers were assigned higher scores, indicating high anxiety, while negative answers were assigned lower scores, indicating low anxiety. The average of all the responses for each participant was calculated to obtain a final score.

The results showed that out of the total participants, 42 exhibited a high level of anxiety in speaking English, while 10 exhibited a low level of anxiety. This was determined by comparing the scores obtained from the questionnaire. The two teachers who participated in the study were also included in the analysis.

In addition to the FLCAS questionnaire, the researcher used the specific anxiety forms proposed by Young (1991, p. 430) and Bailey (1983) to further analyze the data and interpret the results. These specific anxiety forms likely provided additional insights into the nature and sources of the participants' anxiety in speaking English.

Table-01

Participant	Anxiety sign	Criteria
S1, S25	Nervous Laughing	Expression of anxiety by smiling and touching the head.
S2, S7, S8, S12, S14, S18, S20, S21, S24, S27, S29, S35, S38, S40, S43, S46, S47, S48, S49, S50	Restlessness	Frequent and irregular body movements during speaking
S42, S44	Sighing	Taking long and deep respiration due to lack of comfort-ability and tiredness.
	Restlessness	Frequent and irregular body movements during speaking.
S3, S5, S9, S11, S15, S22, S25, S30, S32, S34	Restlessness	Frequent and irregular body movements during speaking.
	Nervous Laughing	Expression of anxiety by smiling and touching the head.
S31, S33	Frozenness	Forgetting their script and remaining silent.
	Restlessness	Frequent and irregular body movements during speaking.
S39, S41	Voice Distortion	Irregular voice, tone, and rhythm.
	Restlessness	Frequent and irregular body movements during speaking

S19	Frozenness	Forgetting their script and remaining silent.
	Restlessness	Frequent and irregular body movements during speaking.
	Nervous Laughing	Expression of anxiety by smiling and touching the head.
S13, S17, S23, S26, S28, S36, S44	Voice Distortion	Irregular voice, tone, and rhythm.
	Frozenness	Forgetting their script and remaining silent.
	Restlessness	Frequent and irregular body movements during speaking.
	Nervous Laughing	Expression of anxiety by smiling and touching the head.
S1,S4,S6, S10, S16, S37, S42, S45, S51, S52	No anxiety	Feeling comfortable and enjoying speaking in public.

The analysis of the 42 participants who exhibited a high level of anxiety in speaking English revealed that all of them displayed signs of fidgeting during speaking. This physical manifestation of anxiety indicates their discomfort and uneasiness in the language learning process.

Furthermore, the analysis also identified other contributing factors to their anxiety, namely communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and test anxiety. Communication apprehension refers to the participants' fear or anxiety related to engaging in oral communication, particularly in a second language. This fear can stem from concerns about being judged or evaluated by others.

Fear of negative evaluation refers to the participants' worry about receiving negative feedback or criticism from others regarding their English-speaking abilities. This fear can lead to self-consciousness and a reluctance to speak up or take risks in language learning contexts.

Test anxiety, as another contributing factor, relates to the participants' anxiety specifically related to assessments or exams in the English language. This anxiety can be triggered by the pressure to perform well and the fear of making mistakes or being unable to meet expectations during testing situations.

Overall, the analysis highlights the multifaceted nature of anxiety in language learning and the various factors that contribute to it. By identifying these factors, educators and practitioners can better understand the challenges faced by highly anxious learners and develop strategies to address and mitigate their anxiety in the language learning process.

The Factors Affecting Speaking Anxiety of Students

1. Fear of Failure

The analysis of the overall results indicates that fear of failure was a prevalent factor among all fifty student participants in the research. This fear of failure was observed to be present in various aspects of their language learning, including speaking skills and tests. The students exhibited stress and anxiety regarding their performance and were concerned about the possibility of failing.

The fear of failure can have a significant impact on students' motivation and self-confidence. It creates a sense of pressure and can hinder their willingness to take risks and participate actively in the language learning process. This

fear may stem from a variety of factors, such as the desire to meet academic expectations, fear of disappointing oneself or others, or concern about the consequences of failure.

It is important to address and alleviate the fear of failure among language learners. Creating a supportive and encouraging learning environment, providing constructive feedback, and focusing on progress rather than solely on outcomes can help reduce students' anxiety related to failure. Additionally, promoting a growth mindset, which emphasizes the belief that abilities can be developed through effort and practice, can empower students to approach challenges with a positive mindset.

It is worth noting that the two teachers involved in the research also expressed some hesitation and anxiety regarding tests. This highlights the need for supporting teachers as well, as their own anxiety can influence the classroom atmosphere and students' perceptions of language learning.

By addressing and addressing the fear of failure, educators can create a more conducive and supportive learning environment that allows students to feel more confident, take risks, and ultimately enhance their language learning outcomes.

2. Communication Apprehension

The interviews conducted with the participants "S2, S3, S5, S7, S8, S9, S11, S12, S13, S14, S15, S17, S18, S19, S20, S21, S22, S23, S24, S25, S26, S27, S28, S29, S30, S31, S32, S33, S34, S35, S36, S38, S39, S40, S41, S43, S44, S46, S47, S48, S49", revealed that communication apprehension played a significant role in their anxiety during speaking English. The participants expressed feelings of anxiety when asked about their experiences of speaking English, attributing it to communication apprehension lapses. They identified several factors that contributed to their anxiety, including a lack of linguistic knowledge, limited vocabulary, grammar weaknesses, mispronunciation, shyness, a high heartbeat rate, and nervousness.

The participants also shared some strategies they used to cope with their anxiety. These strategies included body movement, controlled breathing, avoiding eye contact with the audience, and smiling. These techniques were employed by the participants as a way to manage their anxiety and alleviate the discomfort they experienced during English speaking activities.

Overall, the findings suggest that communication apprehension, stemming from various language-related challenges and self-consciousness, contributes to speaking anxiety among the participants. The participants' anxiety manifested in their physical reactions and behaviors, such as fidgeting and avoiding eye contact. Addressing these contributing factors and providing support in developing linguistic skills, vocabulary, and confidence in speaking English can help alleviate communication apprehension and reduce speaking anxiety among language learners.

3. Test Anxiety

The interviews conducted with participants S51 and S52 revealed that they also experienced speaking anxiety, although they initially responded with "no anxiety" when asked directly. When asked about the factors contributing to their anxiety, they identified a lack of linguistic knowledge as the main cause. They mentioned that their limited proficiency in English created anxiety during speaking activities.

Furthermore, when the participants were asked how they handled their anxiety, they mentioned avoiding eye contact as a coping mechanism. This suggests that they used this strategy to manage their discomfort and alleviate their anxiety during English speaking tasks.

To further assess their anxiety levels, the interviewer conducted a speaking activity in the classroom without any prior practice. As a result, both participants experienced increased heart rate and became visibly anxious during the task.

This suggests that their anxiety was triggered by the combination of their lack of linguistic competence and the pressure of speaking a foreign language in a test-like situation.

From these findings, it can be inferred that participants in this category faced speaking anxiety primarily due to their limited linguistic skills and the fear of performing poorly in English speaking activities. Addressing their linguistic competence through targeted language instruction and providing support to build their confidence in speaking English can help reduce their anxiety and enhance their language learning experience.

4. Fear of Negative Evaluation

Upon careful observation, it was found that participants S5, S7, S8, S9, S11, S12, S13, S14, S15, S17, S18, S19, S20, S21, S22, S23, S24, S25, S26, S27, S28, S29, S30, S31, S32, S33, S34, S35, S36, S38, S39, S40, S41, S43, S44, S46, S47, exhibited significant difficulties in their speaking abilities. When these participants were asked about their anxiety levels while speaking English, all of them expressed a high degree of anxiety, except for the two teacher participants.

Furthermore, during the interviews, signs of fear and negative evaluations were evident among the students. They expressed a fear of negative evaluation, which was identified as one of the key factors contributing to their anxiety when speaking English. The students were afraid that if they made mistakes while speaking, their teachers would point them out and evaluate them negatively.

This fear of negative evaluation created a sense of pressure and heightened anxiety among the students, leading to self-consciousness and reluctance to speak English in front of others. It suggests that the fear of being judged or criticized for their language skills significantly impacted their confidence and hindered their ability to communicate effectively in English.

Addressing this fear of negative evaluation and creating a supportive and non-judgmental learning environment can help alleviate students' anxiety and encourage their active participation in English speaking activities. Providing constructive feedback, emphasizing improvement rather than focusing solely on errors, and promoting a positive classroom atmosphere can contribute to enhancing students' speaking skills and reducing their anxiety levels.

Discussion

Language anxiety plays a significant role in the process of second language acquisition, as it can impede learners' progress in acquiring the target language. Foreign language anxiety encompasses the interplay of self-perception, emotions, and behaviors within the language acquisition classroom, stemming from the unique nature of the language learning process. It is distinct from other forms of anxiety and appears to be closely tied to the linguistic acquisition context, indicating a strong correlation between language learning and associated concerns. The impact of anxiety on students aspiring to learn a foreign language, particularly English, can be both advantageous and detrimental. When students are unable to regulate or control their anxiety, it can hinder their ability to learn English, resulting in poor academic performance. Conversely, anxiety can also serve as a driving force. For instance, if students are anxious about failing an exam, it can motivate them to be more committed to studying the English language. In essence, anxiety is deeply intertwined with a learner's success in acquiring the English language. Additionally, learners with high anxiety levels may encounter greater difficulty in learning English due to their fear of making mistakes during the learning process.

Based on the results of a questionnaire, the researcher identified 42 students with high anxiety, 8 students with mild anxiety, and two anxiety-free teacher participants. The prevalence of high anxiety surpassed that of low-level anxiety. Furthermore, the findings revealed various factors that made students nervous when speaking. Examples include speaking publicly in English in front of the class under the direction of the teacher, receiving unfavorable assessments from the teacher, concerns about grammatical errors, mispronunciation, and being subjected to mockery by others. Communication apprehension, testing anxiety, and fear of unfavorable assessment emerged as three key

characteristics of foreign language anxiety. The anxiety surrounding communication serves as the foundational root of language anxiety, involving the fear of interacting with other individuals. The researcher identified contributing factors that influenced students' performance, such as weaknesses in language components, including grammar, vocabulary development, mispronunciation, and difficulty comprehending the subject matter. The impacts of communication anxiety directly manifest in learners' behavior, with students feeling bashful, ashamed, inferior, confused, lacking focus, and experiencing difficulty expressing themselves. The students exhibited fear and apprehension when it came to communicating with others, including their classmates. A study by Riffat-un-Nisa Awan et al. (2010) identified public speaking as the primary source of anxiety, followed by fears of syntactic errors, mispronunciation, and a lack of spontaneity. Additionally, due to their intense fear of speaking in English, students lacking confidence struggle when required to engage in verbal communication with others. Furthermore, students experiencing "test anxiety" fear performing in front of the class without sufficient preparation. The students expressed the need to prepare before presenting in front of the class as a means to alleviate their anxiety. Physical symptoms of exam anxiety include dizziness, trembling, sweating, an accelerated heart rate, tension, and sweaty palms. These symptoms lead to a loss of focus on the test material, making it more challenging for students to complete the exam as they forget previously memorized content. This indicates that test anxiety is closely linked to an individual's concerns about being evaluated.

In a study conducted by Mohd Fadhli Shah Khaidzir (2015), it was found that students undergoing initial language learning in the interlanguage phase experience varying degrees of anxiety. One significant factor contributing to this anxiety is the fear of negative judgment from the audience, commonly known as the fear of being evaluated. Evaluation refers to the process of assessing the quality of someone's performance, and its effects differ among individuals. Some individuals perceive evaluation as motivating, while others view it as highlighting their shortcomings and feeling inadequate. Many learners expressed that if they were not afraid of making mistakes and being negatively judged by their teachers and peers, they would be more willing to express themselves. Negative feedback from teachers or peers can have a profound impact, as previously mentioned by the researcher. It triggers psychological factors such as shyness, anxiety, confusion, and unease among students. The psychological impacts include confusion, increased heart rate, stammering, and trembling. The respondents also mentioned their fear of receiving unfavorable evaluations from teachers and peers, as they were apprehensive about potential humiliation in the classroom, especially when faced with critical remarks from the teacher. The participants were preoccupied and concerned about how others perceived them, often trying to protect their image by avoiding speaking. For example, the statement "I'm worried my English teacher is ready to correct every mistake I make" captures this apprehension and is relevant to the FLCAS instrument, highlighting the connection between criticism and unfavorable assessment. Additionally, students' anxiety about facing punishment from their teachers significantly influences their level of anxiety. Consequently, many students withdraw from participating in speaking activities. As a result, it is crucial for teachers to educate their students that making mistakes is neither inherently negative nor dangerous, as students can learn and improve from their errors. The fear of receiving undesirable feedback from the audience stems from the learners' concern about appearing ignorant before others. For instance, students often become quiet and experience significant nervousness when asked to perform in class, struggling with their words. This can be attributed to the presence of classmates who may not perform well and receive harsh criticism. The majority of participants expressed a fear of public speaking and standing before the class to say anything. Some participants who displayed an encouraged attitude toward language learning stated that when their teacher asked them to practice speaking in front of their peers, they expressed their concerns about their readiness. On the other hand, other participants with a fearful demeanor expressed worry when their teacher requested them to speak in front of the class.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is crucial for language teachers to address and alleviate anxiety in the classroom in order to create a conducive learning environment. They should employ various activities and teach through casual conversations, discussions, jokes, and other informal methods in the English language classroom. This approach helps to reduce fear and anxiety among students. The findings and implications of this study can be applicable to similar EFL settings in the region, in Asia, and even in other parts of the world, as the study was conducted in a general EFL setting.

In summary, the careful analysis and description of the study revealed that speaking anxiety had negative effects on students' speaking abilities. Students experienced pressure, lack of confidence, and hesitation when speaking, leading to difficulties in forming sentences, speaking in front of their peers, and expressing their ideas in the target language. Low self-confidence, perceived lack of competence, and fear of making mistakes were identified as major causes of speaking anxiety, which hindered students' active participation in the classroom. Among the participants, thirty students exhibited a high level of anxiety, while twenty others were moderately affected or in a relatively normal condition.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations can be made:

Provide support and assistance to language learners: Recognize and identify students who experience speaking anxiety and provide them with guidance and support in English classes. This can include one-on-one sessions, additional practice opportunities, and personalized feedback to help reduce their fear and hesitation when speaking.

Create an effortless learning environment: Foster a relaxed and informal atmosphere in the English language classroom. Encourage open communication, establish a supportive classroom community, and create opportunities for students to engage in casual conversations, discussions, and group activities. This can help alleviate anxiety and create a more comfortable environment for language learners.

Provide teacher training: English language teachers should receive training on understanding and managing language anxiety and stress among students. Training should include insights into child psychology and effective strategies for addressing and mitigating speaking anxiety. This will equip teachers with the necessary skills to create a supportive and inclusive learning environment.

Adopt Communicative Language Teaching (CLT): Instead of relying solely on grammar-focused or translation-based methods, employ Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approaches. CLT emphasizes meaningful communication and interaction in the target language, promoting real-life language use and reducing the focus on accuracy and error correction. This approach can help students feel more comfortable and confident in their speaking abilities.

Utilize effective reading strategies: Teachers should modify their approach to teaching reading skills by incorporating effective strategies such as the SQ3R (Survey, Question, Read, Recite, Review) or SQRRR (Survey, Question, Read, Retrieve, Review) methods. These strategies engage students actively in the reading process, enhance comprehension, and provide a structured framework for reading tasks, reducing anxiety associated with reading activities.

By implementing these recommendations, language teachers can create a supportive and effective learning environment that addresses and mitigates speaking anxiety among students, ultimately enhancing their language learning experience and proficiency.

Future Implications

There are several future implications for addressing language anxiety in English language teaching:

Further exploration of interactive teaching techniques: Teachers can continue to explore and implement interactive teaching techniques that promote student engagement and participation in the language learning process. These

techniques can help create a supportive and inclusive classroom environment that reduces speaking anxiety and encourages students to communicate more confidently.

Integration of technology: The use of technology, such as Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL), can be further explored and integrated into English language teaching. Interactive language learning software, online resources, and virtual communication platforms can provide additional opportunities for students to practice their speaking skills in a less intimidating environment.

Collaborative learning: Emphasizing collaborative learning activities, such as group discussions, pair work, and cooperative projects, can foster a sense of community and support among students. By working together and sharing their language learning experiences, students can reduce anxiety and gain confidence in their speaking abilities.

Focus on learner autonomy: Encouraging learner autonomy and self-directed learning can empower students to take control of their language learning journey. Providing guidance on effective language learning strategies, goal setting, and self-assessment can help students develop the confidence and skills needed to overcome anxiety and actively engage in speaking activities.

Research on effective factors: Further research is needed to examine the impact of factors such as technology-based learning and cooperative learning on reducing language anxiety. Investigating the specific effects of these approaches on student anxiety levels can provide a clearer understanding of their effectiveness in addressing speaking anxiety.

By continuously exploring and implementing these strategies, educators can contribute to the ongoing efforts to reduce language anxiety in English language teaching and create a more positive and effective learning environment for language learners.

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